

Determinants of Employee Performance

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the influence of organizational culture on employee performance with work motivation as an intervening variable at the BPJS Employment Kisaran and Kediri branch offices. This research was conducted at BPJS Employment in two branches, namely at the Kisaran Branch Office Jl. Sisingamaraja No. 460, Kisaran, Sendang Sari, Asahan, Asahan Regency, North Sumatra 21211 and at the Kediri Branch Office Jl. Mayor Bismo No.34, Semampir, Kota District, Kediri City, East Java 64121. This type of research is quantitative, the research population is 71 employees and the sample used is also 71 employees and uses a saturated sampling technique. The data collection used was a questionnaire and the data source was primary, the model used was path analysis of the results of this research as follows: Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.435 and a p value of 0.000 < 0.05. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on work motivation with an original sample value of 0.771 and a p value of 0.000 < 0.05. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.474 and a p value of 0.000 < 0.05. Organizational Culture has an indirect and significant positive effect on Employee Performance through Work Motivation with an original sample value of 0.366 and a p value of 0.000

Keywords: organizational culture, work motivation, employee performance

INTRODUCTION

One of the capitals that is very important for a company's ability to compete and keep up with technological and economic advances is quality human resources (HR). The challenges posed by global competition to the business world in this decade Human resource management will become increasingly important in the future. Today, a company's ability to successfully navigate the highly competitive advantage landscape depends solely on its ability to organize and manage its human resources effectively. Working with clear goals and organizational strategy linkages will result in human resource performance.

As a result, each employee is able to understand and practice the company's cultural values, so that they can integrate into the group as a whole and act in accordance with these values. The values, customs, attitudes and work ethics held by all members of an organization are usually related to the culture of the organization. These components are the basis for observing how workers behave, collaborate, and interact with the surrounding environment. If it can help business success. An organization's shared values form its organizational culture, which serves as a guide for employees in their efforts to achieve organizational goals. Usually, the vision, mission and goals of the organization are used to convey this. An organization's norms, as well as the values, beliefs, hopes, assumptions, and philosophies of its members, combine to form its culture. Therefore, its apparent presence in both individual and group behavior is not surprising. The foundation of organizational practices, including how members interact and handle conflict in the workplace, is organizational culture.

In order to increase employee productivity at work, motivation is closely related to efforts to improve employee performance which is influenced by various factors, including those originating from within the employee himself and the environmental conditions concerned. It is hoped that an employee will always be motivated to work in order to have

good performance. The result of an employee's performance at work is the employee's performance. Performance is a summary of an employee's work results during a predetermined period of time. The final result of a task supported by an employee who is equipped with abilities, direction and goals is his performance. Performance is the result of individual or group work in an organization, based on each person's responsibility in achieving organizational goals in a manner that is in accordance with law, morality and ethics. Drive, desire, and the inner drive to complete a task are all forms of motivation. Employee performance in a company may be affected if your superior inspires and motivates your subordinates.

The phenomenon that occurs at the BPJS Employment Kisaran and Kediri Branch Offices is that the organizational culture that occurs is not good for employees so that work motivation does not have a good effect on employees. This causes an organizational culture that is detrimental to employees so that employees perform poorly and are not good for the organization.

METHOD

The type of research carried out by researchers is quantitative, associative research. This kind of research, according to Sugiyono (2018), is essentially a scientific approach to collecting data for specific applications and purposes. This is based on rational, empirical and methodical scientific qualities. This type of research is quantitative associative.

Research Data Source

According to Sugiyono (2018), primary data is a type of data source that provides data collectors with direct access to data. Researchers collect data directly from the initial source or location where the research is conducted.

Population

The population of this study was 71 employees. This population was taken from two BPJS Employment branch offices, namely the Kisaran Branch with 42 employees and the Kediri Branch with 29 employees. According to Sugiyono (2018) Population is a generalized area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to study and then draw conclusions.

Sample

The sample that will be used in this research is the entire population in the BPJS Employment Kisaran Branch and Kediri Branch, namely 71 respondents, in this case the research uses a saturated sampling technique. According to Sugiyono (2018) the sample reflects the size and characteristics of the population. According to Sugiyono (2018) saturated sampling is a sampling technique when all members of the population are sampled. In other words, the entire population is sampled in a census, which is called saturated sampling.

Place and time

This research was conducted at BPJS Employment in two branches, namely at the Kisaran Branch Office Jl. Sisingamangaraja No. 460, Kisaran, Sendang Sari, Asahan, Asahan Regency, North Sumatra 21211 and at the Kediri Branch Office Jl. Mayor Bismo

No.34, Semampir, Kota District, Kediri City, East Java 64121. The research time was 3 months.

Data collection

Researchers distributed questionnaires to collect data for this research, which is also called primary data, namely data that is directly related to the people involved. According to Sugiyono (2018), primary data is a type of data source that provides data to data collectors directly. According to Sugiyono (2018) questionnaire as a data collection method. This is done by asking a series of questions or written statements to the respondent, who is then asked to react.

In this survey, respondents were asked to assess their attitudes, opinions and the way they or a group of people view a social event using the Likert scale measurement method.

Data analysis

Research data management The software for this is smartPLS 3.3.3. The distribution-free PLS (Partially Least Square) methodology assumes no specific data and can work with nominal, categorical, ordinal, interval and ratio data. When using bootstrapping or random multiplication techniques, PLS (Partial Least Square) has no problems with the assumption of normality. Apart from that, PLS (Partial Least Square) does not need to use a specified minimum sample size. Small sample sizes in research can still be used using PLS (Partial Least Square) The analytical approach used in the PLS (Partial Least Square) method is as follows:

1. Outer model analysis

To ensure that the measurement is worthy of being used as a measuring tool (valid and reliable), an outer model analysis is carried out. This model describes the relationship between a latent variable and the indicators in the research. Several indicators indicate the existence of outer model analysis:

- a. **Convergent Validity.** Standard loading factors, which indicate the strength of the correlation between each measurement item (indicator) and its construct, are used to evaluate convergent validity (Ghozali, 2018). This indicator is based on the correlation between item scores/component scores and construct scores. When an individual's reflexive measure correlates more than 0.7 with the expected construct, then the measure is considered highly measured, whereas an outer loading value between 0.5 – 0.6 is considered sufficient (Ghozali, 2018).
- b. **Discriminant Validity,** is a cross-loading measurement model with reflective indication that is based on construction (Ghozali, 2018). In the event that construction tolerances with adjustment items are greater than other construction tolerances, the resulting block size will be more profitable when compared to other block sizes. However, another method to determine discriminant validity is to compare the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE).
- c. **Composite reliability** is a metric used to measure something that is visible in the latent variable coefficient display (Ghozali, 2018). Internal consistency and Cronbach's alpha are two measurement tools used to assess composite reliability. If the measurement results are more than 0.70, this concept can be considered to have a high level of reliability.
- d. **Cronbach's Alpha** is a reliability test conducted to support composite reliability findings. If the Cronbach's alpha value of a variable is more than 0.7 then it can be considered reliable (Ghozali, 2018).

2. Inner Model Analysis

Analyzing the term "inner model" can also refer to "inner relationships, structural models, and substantive theories," which describes the relationship between the final variables and substantive theories (Ghozali, 2018). One way to evaluate the inner model is to use R-square to build the dependent variable, the Stone-Geisser Q-square test for predictive relevance and t test, as well as the significance of the path structural parameters. The inner model evaluation process using PLS (Partial Least Square) begins by checking the R-square of each dependent variable.

3. Hypothesis Testing

The testing hypothesis can be seen in the t-statistic and probability values. For hypothesis testing that uses statistical significance, the 5% alpha t-statistic value is 1.96. Therefore, the criteria for obtaining/estimating the hypothesized value are H_a and H_0 if the t-statistic is more than 1.96. To reject/accept a hypothesis using probability, H_a is rejected if p is less than 0.05. (Ghozali, 2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model Analysis

Measurement model testing (outer model) is used to determine the specifications of the relationship between latent variables and manifest variables. This test includes convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability.

1. Convergent Validity

This test is seen from the loading factor, the value limit is 0.7, as well as the value limits. Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is 0.5, if above this value it is said to be valid. This means that the value for the indicator is said to be valid, if the indicator explains the construct variable with a value > 0.7 . The structural model in this research is shown in the following figure:

Figure 1. Outer Model

The Smart PLS output for loading factors gives the results in the following table: Outer Loadings In this study there is an equation and the equation consists of two substructures for substructure 1

$$Z = b1X + e1$$

$$Z = 0.771X + e1$$

For substructure 2

$$Y = b2X + b3Z + e2$$

$$Y = 0.435X + 0.474Z + e2$$

Table 1. Outer Loadings

	Organizational Culture (X)	Employee Performance (Y)	Work Motivation (Z)
X.1	0.793		
X.2	0.796		
X.3	0.791		
X.4	0.768		
X.5	0.710		
Y.1		0.829	
Y.2		0.823	
Y.3		0.715	
Y.4		0.828	
Y.5		0.782	
Z.1			0.811
Z.2			0.852
Z.3			0.857

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 1 above there is a value for each variable which states that the indicator for each variable is higher than 0.7, which means that each indicator item has a value higher than 0.7 so that the data is declared valid and can continue with further research.

2. Discriminate Validity

Further research to find out valid data using Discriminate Validity, aims to find out whether the cross loading value is greater than other latent variables so as to determine the results of indicators that are highly correlated with the construct. The following table shows the cross loading results from validity testing as follows:

Table 2. Discriminant Validity

	Organizational Culture (X)	Employee Performance (Y)	Work Motivation (Z)
X.1	0.793	0.595	0.558
X.2	0.796	0.586	0.585
X.3	0.791	0.613	0.557
X.4	0.768	0.700	0.620

X.5	0.710	0.581	0.644
Y.1	0.603	0.829	0.626
Y.2	0.681	0.823	0.637
Y.3	0.485	0.715	0.538
Y.4	0.688	0.828	0.696
Y.5	0.696	0.782	0.705
Z.1	0.632	0.623	0.811
Z.2	0.695	0.785	0.852
Z.3	0.607	0.613	0.857

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 2 above there is a cross loading factor for the Organizational Culture variable, the value for each indicator is greater than the cross loading for the other variables, for the cross loading factor for the Employee Performance variable the value for each indicator is greater than the cross loading value for the other variables, for The cross loading factor of the Work Motivation variable for each indicator has a value that is greater than the cross loading of the other variables, so it can be concluded that there is a valid discriminant value.

3. Composite reliability

In composite reliability research to look at each variable with its reliability value and if the variable value is greater than 0.60 then the research is considered reliable and if it is below 0.60 and 0.7 then it is not reliable. There are several blocks to determine whether the research is reliable or not and valid or not, including the Coranbach alpha value, composite reliability and AVE value can be seen in the table below:

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Organizational Culture (X)	0.830	0.881	0.597
Employee Performance (Y)	0.856	0.897	0.635
Work Motivation (Z)	0.793	0.878	0.706

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 3 above, it can be seen in the Cronbach alpha column that the value for each variable is greater than 0.7, which means that the reliability data of the variable is reliable. The composite reliability column has a value greater than 0.6 so it can be explained that each variable is considered reliable because the data is greater than 0.6. You can see from the AVE column that each variable has a value greater than 0.7, which means the data is valid in AVE terms. All variables from the Cronbach alpha column, reliability column and AVE column have values greater than 0.7 and 0.6 so they are considered reliable and valid.

Inner Model Analysis

Evaluation of the structural model (inner model) is carried out to ensure that the basic model created is strong and correct. The inspection stages carried out in the primary model assessment can be seen from several markers, namely:

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Based on data processing that has been carried out using the SmartPLS 3.3.3 program. The R Square value obtained is as follows:

Table 4. R Square Results

	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Employee Performance (Y)	0.732	0.724
Work Motivation (Z)	0.594	0.588

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 4 above there is an R square value for the variable of 0.732 if the percentage is 73.2%, meaning that together the influence of Organizational Culture and Work Motivation has an effect on Employee Performance with a value of 73.2% and the rest is in the other variables. Meanwhile, the R square value of Work Motivation is 0.594 and if the percentage is Work Motivation it is 59.4%, meaning that the influence of the Organizational Culture variable on Work Motivation is 59.4% and the rest is on other variables.

Hypothesis test

After assessing the inner model, the next thing is to assess the connection between the idle builds as suspected in this review. Speculation testing in this review was carried out by looking at T-Statistics and P-Values. Speculation was announced admitting whether the calculated t value was > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05 . Next are the consequences of the direct impact Path Coefficient

Table 5. Path Coefficients (Direct Influence)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Results
Organizational Culture (X) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.435	4,518	0,000	Accepted
Organizational Culture (X) -> Work Motivation (Z)	0.771	14,742	0,000	Accepted
Work Motivation (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.474	5,212	0,000	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 5 above there is a direct influence of each influence between variables and all accepted hypotheses and the explanation is as follows:

1. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.435 and a p value of $0.000 < 0.05$, which means that if organizational culture improves, employee performance will also increase and if it decreases, employee performance will decrease.
2. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on work motivation with an original sample value of 0.771 and a p value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This means that if organizational culture improves well then work motivation will increase and if organizational culture decreases then work motivation will decrease.

3. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.474 and a p value of 0.000 <0.05. This means that if work motivation increases, employee performance will increase and if work motivation decreases, employee performance will also decrease.

Table 6. Path Coefficients (Indirect Influence)

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV I)	P Values	Results
Organizational Culture (X) -> Work Motivation (Z) -> Employee Performance (Y)	0.366	4,669	0,000	Accepted

Source: Smart PLS 3.3.3

In table 6 above there is an indirect influence, the explanation is as follows:

4. Organizational Culture has a significant indirect and positive effect on Employee Performance through Work Motivation with an original sample value of 0.366 and a p value of 0.000. This means that work motivation can be an intervening variable and influence organizational culture on employee performance indirectly.

CLOSING

Conclusion

The conclusions from this research are as follows:

1. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with an original sample value of 0.435 and a p value of 0.000 <0.05.
2. Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on work motivation with an original sample value of 0.771 and a p value of 0.000 <0.05.
3. Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance with an original sample value of 0.474 and a p value of 0.000 <0.05.
4. Organizational culture has a significant indirect and positive effect on employee performance through work motivation with an original sample value of 0.366 and a p value of 0.000.

Suggestion

Suggestions from this research are as follows:

1. For organizations, this research can be used as input and suggestions to make organizations better in dealing with motivation, organizational culture and employee performance.
2. For future researchers, this research can be used as reference material if they create new research with the same title but different research methods.
3. For future researchers, it can be used as a reference for researching variables outside this research

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